

ISic2917

I.Sicily inscription 2917

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Church of the catacomb of S. Giovanni

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

s-shaped (serpentine) interpuncts on ll.2-4

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Hic iacet in pace Domini infa[s] nomi
2. ne Atinodori annorum duo filius
3. Mucia[ni] primiceri de nume[r]o
4. XI(Undeci)manorum felex in Deo □

Apparatus

Text after Manganaro 1993

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645306

Bibliography

Manganaro, G. 1993. Greco nei pagi e latino nelle città della Sicilia romana tra I

e VI sec. d.C.. In Calbi, A., Donati, A., Poma, G.(eds.), *l'epigrafia del villaggio*.
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Agnello, S.L. 1960. Iscrizioni cemenateriali inedite di Siracusa. *Rivista di Archeologia
Cristiana*. 36: 19-42. At 32-33

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